

The confounded interdependencies of ecosystem stability measures: a critique of “Unifying spatial scaling laws of biodiversity and ecosystem stability” by Liang et al.

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Understanding the drivers of variation in ecosystem stability is essential for advancing ecological theory and managing the impacts of global change on ecosystem services. In a recent article published in *Science*, Liang et al. (1) use three scale-dependent measures of stability to assess the stability-area relationships, purporting to uncover universal scaling laws. These stability measures are likely confounded by the fact that they are mathematically correlated with richness (e.g., contain summations across species number). Liang et al. examine the relationship between ecosystem stability (Est) and area size, showing that stability increases with the size of the area sampled (2-4), and is correlated with the species-area relationship (SAR). SARs are frequently exhibited as a log-log regression with slope z . Liang et al show that the z of the Est -area relationship can be decomposed into two components: that from average species stability (SSt) and from species asynchrony (AS).

Liang et al. use formulations from Thibault and Connolly (5) to calculate these three quantities as:

$$Est = \frac{\sum_k^S u_k}{\sqrt{\sum_{k,l} S^2 v_{k,l}}} \quad eq(1)$$

$$SSt = \frac{\sum_k^S u_k}{\sum_k^S \sqrt{v_{kk}}} \quad eq(2)$$

$$AS = \frac{\sum_k^S \sqrt{v_{kk}}}{\sqrt{\sum_{k,l} S^2 v_{k,l}}} \quad eq(3)$$

Where, μ is the temporal mean abundance of species k , $v_{k,l}$ is the covariance between species k and species l , and $v_{k,k}$ is the variance of species k .

Liang et al. then show how these components vary across area, and specifically that there is a strong Est -area relationship which can be partitioned into SSt and a AS -area relationship. Below I show 1) how these conclusions are driven by confounding aspects of the equations, and 2) the data analyses presented in Liang et al can be reproduced with randomly generated data.

Liang et al found that the slope of the SAR directly correlated with the slope of the AS -area relationship, which then correlated with the Est -area relationship. They also found that,

while the SSt-area relationship was correlated with the ESt-area relationship, it was independent of the SAR. They concluded that AS and SSt were independent pathways to ecosystem stability. This is perhaps true, but these conclusions are the inevitable result from the formulations of the calculations used, and are reproduced with random data.

Mathematically, ESt, AS, and SSt have linked properties, which manifest as differential relationships with the SAR. Here I go through each of these three variables and show how they potentially covary with each other and the SAR. The SAR is a classic relationship often formulated as:

$$\log(S) = \log(c) + z \cdot \log(A) \quad \text{eq(4)}$$

Where S is the number of species predicted in a region or sample of area A . And c is the intercept or number of species found in the smallest sampling area and z is the log-log slope and is influenced by factors like species body size, mobility, or habitat heterogeneity(6).

I support my contention that the findings of Liang et al. are the result of the confounded nature of the equations, rather than ecological mechanisms, in two independent assessments. First, I simplify the equations to highlight the confounded nature when examining them with the SAR. Secondly, I simulated randomly varying species populations and estimate Est, AS, and SSt from eqs 1-3 and show how the analyses in Liang et al. are consistent with the results from simulated data.

1) Highlighting the confounded nature of the equations with SAR

Here I examine eqs 1-3, then apply simplifying assumptions and examine how they theoretically relate to the SAR. I start with ecosystem stability, Est (eq(1)).

To simplify, I use *cov* to refer to the covariance component and *var* the variance component of total variance. Further, if we assume temporal mean abundances, u , the variances, and covariances are randomly sampled from normal distributions, then we can make the summation of mean abundance equal the average multiplied by the number of species and the denominator to separate the covariance and variance components multiplied by the number of species-level estimates (S^2-S for covariances since it is a matrix minus the diagonal), we get:

$$Est = \frac{S \cdot \bar{u}}{\sqrt{(S^2-S) \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} + S \cdot \bar{v}_{var}}} \quad \text{eq(5)}$$

Obviously, assuming that quantities like temporal average abundances and variances are randomly drawn from a normal distribution is unrealistic, since ecological mechanisms will create interdependencies, but the point is to show that the underlying equations generate strong expectations on the relationships in Liang et al. Later, I will briefly discuss how ecological mechanisms should alter the relationships predicted by random data.

We simply reconfigure eq(5) to estimate richness:

$$S = \frac{Est \cdot \sqrt{S^2 \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} - S \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} + S \cdot \bar{v}_{var}}}{\bar{u}} \quad \text{eq(6)}$$

Then we take the log of this and insert this into the SAR and solve for $\log(Est)$:

$$\log(Est) = \log(c) + z \cdot \log(A) + \log(\bar{u}) - \log(\sqrt{S^2 \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} - S \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} + S \cdot \bar{v}_{var}}) \quad \text{eq(7)}$$

Therefore, the Est-area relationship (Est.SAR) is just the SAR adjusted by the inequality of mean abundance and square root of richness and the variance and covariance components. Giving $Est.SAR = SAR + X$, where X is the inequality $\log(\bar{u}) - \log(\sqrt{S^2 \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} - S \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} + S \cdot \bar{v}_{var}})$, and we should expect that the latter part of this inequality is likely to be larger in magnitude than $\log(\bar{u})$, meaning that the log-log slope of Est.SAR should be lower than for SAR.

Next, I examine species stability, SSt (eq(2)) and simplify similar to above:

$$SSt = \frac{S \cdot \bar{u}}{S \cdot \sqrt{v_{var}}} = \frac{\bar{u}}{\sqrt{v_{var}}} \quad \text{eq(8)}$$

In eq(8), richness cancels out and so there is no relationship with species richness and hence SSt is theoretically independent of the SAR.

$$\log(SSt) = \log(\bar{u}) - \log(\sqrt{\bar{v}_{var}}) \quad \text{eq(9)}$$

Finally, species asynchrony, AS (eq(3) is simplified:

$$AS = \frac{S \cdot \bar{v}_{var}}{\sqrt{(S^2 - S) \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} + S \cdot \bar{v}_{var}}} \quad \text{eq(10)}$$

Then we reconfigure to estimate richness:

$$S = \frac{AS \cdot \sqrt{S^2 \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} - S \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} + S \cdot \bar{v}_{var}}}{\bar{v}_{var}} \quad \text{eq(11)}$$

And then insert into the SAR, resulting in a similar relationship as eq(7):

$$\log(AS) = \log(c) + z \cdot \log(A) + \log(\bar{v}_{var}) - \log(\sqrt{S^2 \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} - S \cdot \bar{v}_{cov} + S \cdot \bar{v}_{var}}) \quad \text{eq(12)}$$

Therefore, the asynchrony-area relationship (AS.SAR) is just the SAR adjusted by the inequality mean variance and sqrt of richness and the variance and covariance components, just like with ESt.

To further simplify and to make the confounding problem more apparent, I assume that both the average covariance and variance are 1, such that $\bar{v}_{cov} = 1$ and $\bar{v}_{var} = 1$. This is obviously unrealistic, and that real data will deviate from this, but it helps make the problem clear. It is obvious that the ESt-area relationship (ESt.SAR) is correlated with the AS-area (AS.SAR) relationship and both with the SAR. Further, there is no SSt-area relationship (SSt.SAR), but should be correlated with ESt.SAR because they share dependency on species abundances, $\log(\bar{u})$:

$$\log(ESt) = SAR + \log(\bar{\mu}) - \log(\sqrt{S^2 + 2S}) \quad \text{eq(13)}$$

$$\log(SSt) = \log(\bar{\mu}) \quad \text{eq(14)}$$

$$\log(AS) = SAR - \log(\sqrt{S^2 + 2S}) \quad \text{eq(15)}$$

This natural mathematical relationship between ESt, SSt, and AS (e.g., equations 13-15) always returns the set of relationships shown by Liang et al. in their structural equation model shown in their Fig. 5B, with completely random data. Further, you do not actually need variances or asynchrony to recover the relationships reported by Liang et al.

2) Numerical confirmation

I ran simulations of species with randomly varying abundances through time using the Liang et al. equations 1-3 (i.e., not using the simplified derivations shown above), and it is clear that the dependencies shown in the equations above are recovered with random data, and that the results in Liang et al. are likely just reflecting these artifacts. Using the SAR parameters from He et al. (7), $c = 5.96$, $z = 0.2$ and simulating communities over 30 years with a maximum species pool of 100 species, minimum community size of 4 species, maximum community of 24 species, average abundance of 50 and sampling standard deviation of 30, I calculated ESt, SSt, and AS, and the log-log slopes of their relationships with area (as analyzed in Liang et al.) (see R-code). As predicted, ESt and AS strongly covary with area (Fig. S1), but SSt does not (Fig. S1). Moreover, it should be readily apparent that ESt and AS are recovering basically the same relationship with area.

As a result of the shared mathematical properties, SSt does correlate with ESt, but rather weakly, because they are only linked by abundances and not a shared dependency on richness. However, AS strongly predicts ESt, because of the shared reliance on richness (Fig. S2). This correlation difference in the two panels in Fig. S2 results in Liang et al.'s inferences that asynchrony is more important for ecosystem stability.

Moreover, there's always a positive correlation between the log-log regression z coefficients for SAR and ESt.SAR. If we examine the relationships presented in Liang et al. (e.g., their figures 3, 4 and 5), we can see that random data reproduces their main findings. Specifically, the simulations based on randomly varying populations returns a very strong relationship between the z -coefficients of AS.SAR and ESt.SAR and a weaker relationship between SSt.SAR and ESt.SAR (Fig. S3). Further, the z -coefficient of the SAR strongly predicts the z -coefficient of AS.SAR (Fig. S3). Liang et al.'s Fig 5B shows that the standardized coefficient of the correlation between the z -coefficient of AS.SAR and ESt.SAR was 0.99, while the correlation between the z -coefficients of SSt.SAR and ESt.SAR was only 0.36, qualitatively very similar to the results from random data presented in the top row of Fig. S3.

Further, simulating log-log slopes across 100 random assemblages reveals that the z -coefficients of ESt.SAR are a constant proportion of those for the SAR (about 0.5 with the

parameters used), as is the case for the z-coefficients of Ast.SAR with SAR (Fig. S4). However, the z-coefficients for SSt.SAR have no relationship with those from the SAR (Fig. S4).

Summary

The relationships between ecosystem stability (ESt), species stability (SSt) and species asynchrony (AS) can deviate from those shown in the simulated data above if the SAR is weak, for example when combining data across biomes (8). Further, highly non-random relationships between richness, abundance, and variance can deviate from these predicted relationships in ecologically meaningful ways. We should expect that real-world data would cause greater deviations from the underlying SARs, especially as variance and covariance components increase, which should be the case in hyperdiverse systems or assemblages with short-lived species. The point is that these underlying correlations need to be addressed before making ecological inferences about either stability-area or stability-richness relationships.

The relationships between ESt, SSt and AS presented by Liang et al. are all mathematically linked through their shared parameters. Because ESt and AS are confounded with richness, they have inevitable relationships with the species-area relationship. The relationships presented in the figures of Liang et al. are precisely what is expected from randomly generated data because of these mathematical dependencies. In order to assess the effect of AS and SSt on ESt, one would need to use residuals or calculate standardized effect sizes from null models that control for the underlying SAR.

Fig. S1: The relationships between $\log(\text{area})$ and species richness (which is perfectly linear because the simulations construct the assemblages on this relationship), ecosystem stability (EST), species stability (SSt), and species asynchrony (AS).

Fig. S2: The relationship between EST and both of SSt and AS.

Fig. S3: The relationship between the z-coefficients of the ESSt-area relationship with those from the AS and SSt-area relationships (top row). The relationship between the z-coefficients of both the AS-area relationship and SSt-area relationship with the z-coefficients from the SAR (bottom row).

Fig. S4: Histograms from 100 simulations of the ratio between the z-coefficients for each of ESSt-area, SSt-area, and AS-area relationships to that from the SAR.

Literature cited

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